

Supporting information for

**Evidence for sea water retreat with advent of Meghalayan era (~4200 a BP)
in a coastal Harappan settlement**

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S1 : Study Area: Geology, Geomorphology

Lothal is one of the fascinating remnants of the ancient Harappan (also known as ~ Indus Valley) civilization, which was first excavated by Dr. S.R Rao, ASI, during 1955. Lothal, situated 23 km from the present-day shoreline (Pandya et al., 1977; Vora et al., 2006; Gaur et al., 2006) is believed to be one of the most ancient dockyards (Rao et al., 1979, Khadkikar et al., 2004, Gaur et al., 2006). The Lothal site is believed to have been occupied during the 5600 yr BP to 3800 yr BP, and the reasons of its abandonment are yet to be ascertained (Vora et al., 2006). The site was used as trade center with maritime trade link with western Asia and Africa (Gaur and Vora, 1999). Lothal was connected with other important cities of Sindh by ancient tributary of Sabarmati, i.e., Bhogavo River. The Sabarmati River originates from the Aravalli

ranges and drains southwards in the Gulf of Khambat. The geological framework of mainland Gujarat suggests that the study area as well as the major part of mainland Gujarat is covered by Quaternary sediments of fluvial to aeolian origin (Merh, 1995).

A precise elevation of 7.1 ± 0.1 m above the high water line, was measured at the top of the LH trench site, based on a Real Time Kinematics survey using a Differential Global Positioning System (D-GPS). The accuracy of the D-GPS measurements (better than ± 0.1 m) was verified by taking multiple trench depth readings, which were simultaneously measured using a conventional measuring tape.

The nearest tide station is at Bhavnagar ($\sim >80$ km south), which has a tidal range of approx ~ 12 m (www.tides4fishing.com). The data was available in Mean lower low water (convention used in Indian tide gauge stations) which was converted to Mean Sea Level datum. The Mean High Water (MHW) was 8.8m above msl, the Mean Low Water (MLW) was 1.8m msl, the High Astronomical Tide (HAT) was 11.1m msl whereas the Mean Tide Level (MTL) was 5.3m msl.

S2: Chronology

Sand grains at the bottom of the sequence were dated to be 3080 ± 400 BCE and foraminifers at the 0.5 m depth from the top yield date 2070 ± 215 yr BP (336 BCE–94 CE) (Table S1 and S2). The horizon at 2.5 m depth was dated using both foraminifera C-14 content and OSL of sand grains; both gave an overlapping age ~ 4200 yr BP (OSL: 4330 ± 400 yr BP; AMS ^{14}C : 4150 ± 230 yr BP). Additionally, a horizon at 2.1 m depth was dated using foraminifera AMS C-14 content which yielded an age of 3625 ± 200 yr BP (Table S2). Hence, the depositional record provides depositional history of the entire Meghalayan era and prior $\sim 5030 - 2070$ yr BP.

TABLE S1: OSL CHRONOLOGY OF LOTHAL (LH) SITE AND EQUIVALENT HARAPPAN PHASES.

Sample no	Depth (m)	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	K (%)	Cosmic ray dose rate ($\mu\text{Gy}/\text{a}$)	Dose rate ($\mu\text{Gy}/\text{a}$)	CA M <i>De</i> (gy)	CAM A <i>ge</i> (ka)	Over-dispersion (%)	Median Age In yr BP	Equivalent Harappan phase (Kenoyer, 1998; Possehl, 2002)
ISR- 71	3.4	1.3 ± 0.06	14.2 ± 0.7	0.41 ± 0.01	153 ± 40	1522 ± 130	7.7 ± 0.2	5.1 ± 0.4	26	5030 ± 400	Early Harappan
ISR 372	2.5	1.1 ± 0.06	15.9 ± 0.8	0.38 ± 0.01	163 ± 36	1588 ± 136	6.9 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.4	24	4330 ± 400	Mature Harappan

TABLE 2: AMS ¹⁴C DATE AND ITS CALIBRATED RANGE.

Lab No	Dept h (m)	14C age ± 1σ	Calibrated age ±2σ		Med -ian age BP/	Calibrated age ±2σ		Med -ian age BCE / CE	Equivalent Harappan Phase (Kenoyer., 1998; Possehl., 2002)
			Calendar Year	Calendar Year		Calendar Year	Calendar Year		
			Max	Min			Max	Min	
			(BP)	(BP)			(BC E)	(BCE/C E)	
Poz- 103208	0.50	2450± 35	1856	2285	2070 ± 215 BP	336	94	120± 215 BCE	----
D-AMS 042905	2.13	3727± 24	3424	3825	3625 ± 200 BP	1874	1475	1675 ± 200 BCE	Late Harappan
IUACD# 20C3314	2.50	4132± 42	3918	4385	4150 ± 230 BP	2437	1969	2200 ± 200 BCE	Mature Harappan

Note: Radiocarbon date is calibrated by using Calib8.20 (Marine20.14c) online software. The marine reservoir correction ($\Delta R = -106 \pm 51$) is taken from the nearest station (i.e. Pirotan Island, 70.0E; 22.6N) to the Lothal along the Gujarat coast (Source: <http://calib.org/calib/calib.html>).

All the cited chronology in the paper has been converted into “yr BP”. In addition to the same, the entire chronology of the LH trench section, too, (both OSL and AMS ages) has been converted into the “yr BP” ages in order to maintain the chronological synchronicity with respect to the archaeological context.

S3: Micropalaeontology

A total of thirty-four representative samples covering all litho units of the sequence were analyzed for the micropalaeontological study. A three-step technique (soaking, sieving, and drying) was used for 50 g of each bulk sediment in the laboratory to prepare and concentrate the sample for examination. The sediment sample was soaked in distilled water with 5 ml of

sodium hexa-meta-phosphate to disaggregate and disperse the mud; the sample was then washed through a sieve with 63-micron mesh openings (Synder and Huber, 1996). In the laboratory, a fraction of >63-micron sediment samples were collected and oven dried at 50 °C (close to room temperature) to avoid the potential loss of agglutinated foram tests (Synder and Huber, 1996). The dried sample was further observed with a stereoscopic binocular microscope (Fig S1). Approximately 300 foraminifera specimens were picked, and the number of foraminifera specimens per species per sample was calculated for representative samples. The number of foraminifer specimens were counted on per gram basis for all the samples and termed as Total Foraminifera Number (TFN), which is used as a measure of abundance of calcareous foraminifers in the sediments. The classification criteria (Loeblich and Tappan 1988; Sen Gupta, 1999; Milker and Schmiedl, 2012) was applied here for foraminifera classification. The microfossil assemblage in the LH trench sediment contained foraminifers (Fig S1). The relative percentages of major foraminifer assemblage (*Ammonia-Elphidium assemblage*, *Globigerinoides* and *Bolivina*) were counted and TFN was calculated. Units 1–4 show higher TFN (>300) with the dominant presence of *Ammonia-Elphidium assemblage* (35–51%), planktic *Globigerinoides* (6–24%), *Bolivina* (1–12%), and small amounts of gastropods and ostracods. However, in contrast the overlying units 5 and 6 showed a gradual reduction in the content of TFN (<300) (*Ammonia*: 65-76%, *Bolivina*: 3-17% and *Globigerinoides*: 2–13%) hinting towards the gradual dominance of the estuarine environment in the LH trench site.

Figure S1: Photomicrograph of selected foraminifers extracted from LH sedimentary record.

S4: X-Ray Fluorescence Analysis

For the geochemical analysis (major and trace elements), the samples were dried at 50°C and further crushed to a size of <63 µm. The crushed samples were packed in sample cups using a thin propylene film and were analyzed in XEPOS HE XRF at the Institute of Seismological Research, India. The analytical precision was checked using replicate measurements better than 5% and 10% for major and trace elements (Das et al., 2017). The ratio of TiO₂/Al₂O₃ was used, to determine the role of the provenance change within the Bhogawo river channel. Whereas, the ratio of K₂O/Al₂O₃ was used, as an indicator of the chemical weathering intensity in the source area (Yarincik et al., 2000; Bloemsma et al., 2012). The ratio of TiO₂/Al₂O₃ tends to increase with the increase in the marine influence within the Bhogawo channel. This increase is attributed to the tidal channel which brings in materials from longshore currents which are often derived from Deccan Trap rich sources (Saha et al., 2012).

S5: Total Carbon (TC), Total Sulphur (TS), and Stable Isotopic Composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$)

Content of carbon, sulphur and their isotopes ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$) are often modulated by the plants and environments of their origin. Various environments show characteristic values, which are often used to deduce past environmental conditions (Deines P., 1980; Veizer et al., 1999; Agnihotri et al., 2008; Yu et al., 2010). In present study the sediment samples were powdered and stored overnight in a hot air oven at ~55°C for complete moisture removal. The required amounts (~30–40 mg) of dried samples were packed in tin capsules to measure the TC%, TS%, and stable isotopic ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$). The instrumental setup was comprised of an Elemental Analyser (EA; model VARIO Isotope Select) and Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer (IRMS; model Isoprime precision) at the Birbal Sahni Institute of Palaeosciences, Lucknow, India. The accuracy and reproducibility of the generated data was checked by running a suite of international IAEA-supplied reference standards and two laboratory (control) standards: ϵ -

Amino-n-Caproic acid [$C_6H_{15}NO_2$] (abbreviated as ACA) and IAEA-S2 and IAEA-S3 (both silver sulphide compounds) were principally used for the primary calibration of the isotopic data. Sulphanilamide (the BSIP internal standard) was frequently used for assessing analytical precision better than ~2–3% for C and S concentrations and ~0.2‰ for isotopic data (for details refer to Agnihotri et al., 2020).

S6: Clay Mineralogy

For the clay mineralogy analysis, oriented clay sample slides were prepared by pipetting 1 ml of clay solution onto a glass slide and air dried. The clay slides were treated with ethylene glycol for 1 hr at 100 °C and scanned from 3–30° 2 Θ at 1° 2 Θ /min on a Rigaku X-ray diffractometer using Ni-filtered and Cu K α radiation. The slides were scanned from 24° to 26° 2 Θ at 1/2° 2 Θ /min to differentiate between kaolinite and chlorite peaks. Clay minerals were identified by the basal (001) diffraction lines on glycolated samples. Four major clay minerals (smectite, illite, kaolinite, and chlorite) were identified and semi-quantified following Biscaye (1965); the peak area ratios were calculated.

S7: Relative Sea Level Index Point

Past changes in the sea stand have often been studied based on marine limiting, foraminifera distribution, $\delta^{13}C$ and $\delta^{34}S$ distribution in sediments (Horton and Edwards, 2006; Engelhart et al., 2009; Kemp et al., 2009, 2010, 2012; Engelhart et al., 2013). Well dated sedimentary sequences with precise information of foraminiferal assemblage, distribution of isotopic fractions of Carbon and Sulphur along with presence of characteristic marine dwelling diatoms/organisms and information pertaining to elevation and tidal range, are best suited to infer magnitude of past sea stand (Engelhart et al., 2013). In order to estimate the relative sea stand change, we used the information pertaining to indicative meaning in terms of age, location, relationship of sample with tidal datum and calculated errors involved in all associated parameters (Shennan, 1986; Van de Plassche, 1991; Kemp et al., 2009; Horton et al., 2009; Engelhart et al., 2009; Engelhart and Horton, 2012).

Based on the relationship suggested by Engelhart and Horton, (2012) the Relative Sea Level

Index point is calculated as,

$$RSL_i = A_i - RWL_i \quad (1)$$

Where, RSL_i is the Relative Sea Level Index point, A_i is the depth of the sample in the trench, where trench top altitude was established precisely with respect to tidal datum and RWL_i is the Reference Water Level. In addition to that it is important to assess the error involved in each RSL estimated. Every sample has an error involved, depending on parameters used to estimate the relative sea stand (Shennan, 1986; Engelhart and Horton, 2012). The cumulative error is expressed as

$$E_i = (e_1^2 + e_2^2 + e_n^2)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Where e_1 =altitude error, e_2 =benchmark value error, e_3 =sampling thickness error and e_4 = sampling interval error.

For error calculations, we considered the error values as, e_1 =altitude error = ± 0.1 m, e_2 =benchmark value error = ± 0.1 m, e_3 =sampling thickness error = ± 0.0125 m, e_4 = sampling interval error = ± 0.025 m.

S8: Archaeological Context

Datasets from various coastal Harappan sites indicate that coastal settlements were often profoundly involved in trade activities (Rao, 1979; Gaur and Vora, 1999; Vora et al., 2006) and less dependent on agrarian culture. The shoreline stood landward from 3000–2000 BCE with a peak stand ≥ 1 m above current msl (Hashimi et al., 1995; Banerji et al., 2015; Das et al., 2017; Makwana et al., 2019 and present study). For example, Lothal had a dockyard approximately ~ 23 km from the present-day shoreline. Despite its riverine nature, the dockyard was likely not dry at any time of the year and helped settlers in Lothal perform maritime trade practices with the Middle East. This would only be possible if the riverine route was under the influence of a tidal environment that ensured the year-round presence of water in an otherwise present ephemeral river. The present investigation at the LH site suggests that the area experienced marine environment from >5000 yr BP–1200 yr BP (Fig. 3). This agrees with the peak of the Middle Holocene high sea stand from 5000–4000 yr BP (Hashimi et al., 1995;

Das et al., 2017). The present-day elevation of 7.1 ± 0.1 m msl of the LH site and the depth of the estuarine zone indicate a marine limiting higher sea stand ($\sim 1.2 \text{ m} \pm 0.2 \text{ m}$ msl) during the pre-Meghalayan period (Early and Mature Harappan phase) which continued up to beginning of the Christian era (Fig. 2).

The falling sea stand after ~ 4200 yr BP possibly eliminated the marine influence, which (along with monsoonal aridity) resulted in a complete scarcity of water (Fig. 2). Hence, the Lothal port could no longer support ship transport. The region might have witnessed estuarine influence upto ~ 2070 yr BP, but it appears it could not support ship movements. Therefore, we surmise that the sea stand fall occurred after the beginning of the Meghalayan era caused the dockyard at Lothal to be dysfunctional. Our results, despite the lack of precision in ascertaining the exact timing of the transition environmental changes, suggest marine environment at the LH site prior to and at 4200yr BP and an estuarine conditions upto ~ 2070 yr BP. This information, coupled with that from other studies, strongly favors changes in the Middle Holocene Sea stand with a peak from 5000–4000 yr BP and a gradual fall approximately 4000 yr BP. We argue that the sea stand fall—coinciding with the end of the Mature Harappan era—adversely impacted maritime trade of ancient settlers. Hence, our study suggests the plausible role of sea level change at the circa inception of the Meghalayan period (the terminal part of the Mature Harappan phase $\sim 4150 - 3625$ yr BP) that likely coincided with a period of global aridity.